

Syntax - Stepped Exponential Survival Analysis

Document Information

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Introduction

This document includes detailed information and syntax on the dropout analysis for the Züri Can study. This information will enable you to run a simulation of the analysis. For more information on the framework of the study, the method, and the results of the analysis, please see the document *Nordt, C., Buschner, M., Herdener, M., & Heckel, N. (2026). Züri Can Study Dropout Analysis 2023-2025 (Version 1). Zenodo.*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20409717>.

Syntax (SAS 9.4M9)

- * Let us assume that a three-year longitudinal study has mandatory bi-annual
- * surveys that must be completed within an eight-week period. If the survey is
- * not completed by the deadline, study participation automatically ends.
- * However, participation can also end at any point for other reasons.

- * Simulation of dropouts with two groups (n = 500 each), who have different dropout rates:
- * Group A has an annual dropout of 10% ('r0=0.10') and group B of 20% ('r0=0.20').
- * Group A has a much higher step function ('s0=0.80') than group B ('s1=0.20');

```
%Let n = 500; *Set the number 'n' for group A and group B (identical size);
%Let r0 = 0.10; *Set the constant annual dropout rate 'r0' for group A;
%Let r1 = 0.20; *Set the constant annual dropout rate 'r1' for group B;
%Let s0 = .80; *Set the proportion of the step function 's0' of group A;
%Let s1 = .20; *Set the proportion of the step function 's1' of group B;
%Let ymax = 3; *Set the maximum observation time in years;
```

- * Time is variable 't' in days and 'y' in years;
- * If censored then 'c=1' else 'c=0';
- * '57' days is the end of the eight-weeks period;
- * '183' days is the interval between the surveys;

Note: In the Züri Can study, the method for calculating the online survey due date was slightly adjusted during the course of the study. This requires specific care when defining the day when a participant is ultimately excluded due to not completing the online survey. For the second survey, the exclusion date was calculated as day 239 after becoming eligible to purchase study cannabis in 84 cases, as day 240 in 39 cases, as day 241 in 25 cases, and as day 242 in 21 cases. For simplicity, we used t = 240 for all 169 cases. Similarly, for the third survey, t = 424 was corrected to t = 423, and for the fourth survey, t = 605, t = 607 and t = 608 were corrected to t = 606. No correction was necessary for the fifth survey (t = 789).

- * Data simulation using the values provided;

```
data simu (drop= t_);
call streaminit(68351); /* Set seed for reproducibility */
length group_ $1;
group_ = 'A';
group = 0;
do id = 1 to &n;
t_ = ceil(rand('Weibull',1,365.25/&r0));
If rand('Bernoulli',&s0) = 1 then t = max(0,183+57+183*ceil(max(0,t_ - (57+183))/183));
Else t = t_;
c = 0;
```

```

If t gt round(&ymax*365.25) Then
do;
t = round(&ymax*365.25);
c = 1;
end;
y = t/365.25;
output;
end;
group_ = 'B';
group = 1;
do id = 1+&n to &n*2;
t_ = ceil(rand('Weibull',1,365.25/&r1));
If rand('Bernoulli',&s1) = 1 then t = max(0,183+57+183*ceil(max(0,t_ - (57+183))/183));
Else t = t_;
c = 0;
If t gt round(&ymax*365.25) Then
do;
t = round(&ymax*365.25);
c = 1;
end;
y = t/365.25;
output;
end;
run;

```

* This is the syntax that extracts the values used from the simulated data;
* 'fita' is the unweighted PDF of the exponential distribution;
* 'fitb' is the unweighted PDF of the stepped exponential distribution;
* 'sa' is the weight of the step function;
* 'fitc' is the weighted CDF of the stepped exponential distribution;

```

proc nlmixed data=simu gconv=0;
parm r0=.1 r1=0 s0=0 s1=0;
linr = log(365.25/r0)-r1*group;
ra = exp(-linr);
lins = s0 + s1*group;
sa = exp(lins)/(1+exp(lins));
fita = exp(-(ra*(t-1)))-exp(-(ra*t));
fitb = (mod(t-57,183)=0) *
( (t ne 57) *
( (t = 57+183) * (1 - exp(-ra*t))
+ (t ne 57+183) * (exp(-(ra*(t-183))) - exp(-(ra*t)))
)
);
fitc = exp(-(ra*t))*(1-sa) + exp(-(ra*(floor((t-57)/183)*183+57)*(t ge 57 + 183)))*sa;

```

```
fit = fita*(1-sa)+fitb*sa;
ll = log(fit)*(c=0)+log(fitc)*(c=1);
model t ~ general(ll);
predict fitc out=predc;
estimate "r0 (set = &r0)" r0;
estimate "r1 (set = &r1)" r0*exp(r1);
estimate "s0 (set = &s0)" exp(s0)/(1+exp(s0));
estimate "s1 (set = &s1)" exp(s0+s1)/(1+exp(s0+s1));
run;
```